

Thank you for taking the time to provide detailed feedback on our Data Management Plan (DMP). We appreciate your constructive comments, which have helped us improve the quality and clarity of our plan. In response to your suggestions, we have made several changes and clarifications. Please find a summary of these modifications below:

- **assessment of existing data:** We understood this section of the peer review to be referring to section 1.1.4. and section 2 (Reused Data). We have stated clearly that we are reusing data and described all the source datasets with related licenses in section **1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?**
- **Information on new data:** We have updated section 3.1.1.3 to indicate that we will be using standardized vocabularies and controlled vocabularies for metadata description, improving the overall consistency and interoperability of our dataset. We chose to adopt DataCite schema: “A set of mandatory metadata that must be registered with the DataCite Metadata Store when minting a DOI persistent identifier for a dataset. The domain-agnostic properties were chosen for their ability to aid in accurate and consistent identification of data for citation and retrieval purposes. Sponsored by the DataCite consortium, version 3.0 was recently released in 2013.”
- **Quality assurance of data:** we decided to adopt [Semantic Versioning](#) guidelines.
- **Backup and security of data:** For ensuring back-up data usability and integrity we will rely on Zenodo’s methods for preservation for long-term data integrity.

Once again, we thank you for your valuable feedback, which has significantly contributed to the improvement of our Data Management Plan. We hope that the changes made address your concerns and suggestions effectively. Please do not hesitate to contact us if you have any further questions or require additional clarification.